

A STIFFNESS MODEL FOR UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE BOLTED JOINTS

Yuxing Yang¹, Yi-Qi Wang¹, Xueshu Liu² Yongjie Bao¹ and Hang Gao^{1,*}

¹ Key Lab. for Precision and Non-traditional Machining Technology of Ministry of Education, School of Mechanical Engineering, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian 116024, China

² School of Automotive Engineering, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian 116024, China

Keywords: Composite bolted joints, Through-thickness stiffness, Stress distribution, Analytical model

ABSTRACT

An analytical model was proposed to predict the stiffness of composite joints under preload of the bolt, which was based on the assumption that unidirectional laminate having different contact radii at the longitudinal direction and transverse direction. An elliptical conical pressure envelope was proposed, including an ellipse in-plane pressure distribution and a forth order polynomial through-thickness pressure distribution, which was validated by the finite element method. Different sampling directions are studied to describe the through-thickness pressure distribution at any z location. The results from the analytical method are in accordance with that from the finite element method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Member stiffness of bolted joints has great influence on the performance of the whole assembly, which determines the deformation of the assembly parts and reliability of the bolted joints. Meanwhile, the joint behaviour prediction is based on the accurate prediction of the member stiffness.

Extensive work can be found in terms of the bearing stiffness for isotropic member materials. Motosh [1] proposed the conical and spherical envelopes for the highly stressed portion of the joint, and used a fourth order polynomial to describe the pressure distribution under preload of the bolt. Marshall [2] used a nonintrusive ultrasonic technique to quantify the contact pressure distribution in a bolted connection, in which the effect of actual contact conditions can be determined. It was found that the spread of the contact pressure distribution was in accordance with the precious analytical studies except for the peak contact pressure value. The simplified expressions were found in literature [3] based on the finite element analysis, of which the stiffness was found as a function of the elastic energy in the structure. The numerical method was used to evaluate the member stiffness of the bolted joints in [4], and a dimensionless correction factor was proposed as empirical formulas with considering the dimensions of the joint, grip length as well as Lamé's constant of the member's material. Nassar [5] developed an improved stiffness model for the isotropic material joint with considering similar and dissimilar plate materials. The effect of the grip length-to-diameter ratio, joint sizes, contact radii ratio, hole clearance, and plate material/thickness ratio are investigated. Yang et al. [6-8] conducted a series of works on stiffness prediction; a finite element model was developed to conduct the systematic study on the prediction of the member stiffness including specimen geometries, member materials and contact characteristics [6]; a semi-analytical method, which combines finite element analysis and analytical method, was proposed to accurately evaluation of axis stiffness of bolted member basing on the non-uniform pressure distribution [7]; and the pressure distribution envelope was measured by the I-Scan system, which demonstrated the conical and spherical envelopes [8]. A three-dimensional axisymmetric model based on the theory of elasticity was proposed, in which assumptions of the pressure and semi-apex angle were not necessary, and the model was validated by the finite element method [9]. For orthotropic member materials, the equivalent cylindrical envelope [10] and conical envelope [11] were most used assumptions to describe the pressure distribution under the preload of the bolt.

This study aims to predict the joint stiffness for unidirectional composite laminate based on the elliptical conical pressure envelope assumption. An analytical method (AM) is developed, which consists of through-thickness pressure distribution and in-plane pressure distribution. The finite

* Corresponding author

E-mail: gaohang@dlut.edu.cn

element method (FEM) is used as validation. The results from AM show good agreement with that of FEM.

2 PROPOSED MODEL

For composite bolted joints, the joint stiffness K_c can be described by the preload of the bolt F_c and the deformation of the laminate δ can be expressed as Eq. (1) [1, 5, 11].

$$K_c = \frac{F_c}{\delta} \quad (1)$$

A four-step procedure is conducted to study the stiffness for the unidirectional laminate (UDL). Firstly, the pressure boundary through the thickness is assumed as an elliptical cone. Secondly, an ellipse distribution for in-plane stress is proposed considering different mechanical properties in x- and y-direction. Thirdly, the clamping pressure $\sigma(x, y, z)$ is formulated as a fourth order polynomial in terms of the preload of the bolt F_c . Finally, the joint stiffness K_c is obtained by substituting corresponding value into Eq. (2).

2.1 Through-thickness pressure boundary

An elliptical conical pressure boundary of unidirectional laminate is assumed with envelope angles α along the fiber and β vertical to the fiber as shown in Fig. 1(a) and Fig. 1(b). The semi-major axis a and the semi-minor axis b are determined by

$$a = \frac{\gamma d}{2} + z \tan \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$b = \frac{\gamma d}{2} + z \tan \beta \quad (3)$$

where d is nominal bolt diameter, while γ is the contact radii ratio.

Figure 1 Fully developed elliptical conical pressure boundary envelope of unidirectional laminate for: (a) semi-major axis; (b) semi-minor axis.

2.2 In-plane pressure boundary

As known, composite laminate has different mechanical properties along fiber orientation and

others. Therefore, the in-plane equivalent stress in terms of i -th layer may satisfy an ellipse envelope (Fig. 2), as following equation shows (at local coordinate ox_iy_i):

$$\left(\frac{x_i}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y_i}{b}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (4)$$

Figure 2 In-plane pressure envelope.

2.3 Pressure distribution

The pressure distributions parallel to the fiber direction and vertical to the fiber direction are assumed as the following fourth order polynomial with respect to x, z and y, z respectively, as shown in Fig. 3 (For convenience, the subscript i is omitted subsequently).

$$\sigma(x, z) = A_1x^4 + A_2x^3 + A_3x^2 + A_4x + A_5 \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma(y, z) = B_1y^4 + B_2y^3 + B_3y^2 + B_4y + B_5 \quad (6)$$

Figure 3 Pressure distribution on element dz of the joint.

Thus, the pressure distribution on element dz of the joint may yield the following:

$$\sigma(x, y, z) = \frac{\pi - 2\phi}{\pi} \sigma(x, z) + \frac{2\phi}{\pi} \sigma(y, z) \quad (7)$$

where $\sigma(x, z)$ and $\sigma(y, z)$ are approximation functions in the x-direction and y-direction respectively, while A_k and B_k ($k=1 \sim 5$) are parameters that satisfy the boundary conditions of i -th layer as well as static equilibrium. ϕ is a constant value from 0 to $\pi/2$ in radian, which is the angle between x-direction (fiber direction) and sampling direction (Fig. 2). It is assumed that both σ , gradient of σ and second directional derivative of σ are assumed to be zero at $x=a, y=0$ and $x=0, y=b$. In addition, the second directional derivative of σ are equal to zero at $x=\gamma d/2, y=0$ and $x=0, y=\gamma d/2$, which are close to the bolt head radius.

At $x = \frac{\gamma d}{2}, y = 0, \frac{\partial^2 \sigma}{\partial x^2} = 0$ yields the following equation:

$$12A_1 \frac{\gamma d^2}{2} + 6A_2 \frac{\gamma d}{2} + 2A_3 = 0 \quad (8)$$

At $x = 0, y = \frac{\gamma d}{2}, \frac{\partial^2 \sigma}{\partial y^2} = 0$ yields the following equation:

$$12B_1 \frac{\gamma d^2}{2} + 6B_2 \frac{\gamma d}{2} + 2B_3 = 0 \quad (9)$$

At $x = a, y = 0, \sigma = \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 \sigma}{\partial x^2} = 0$ yields that

$$A_1 a^4 + A_2 a^3 + A_3 a^2 + A_4 a + A_5 = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$4A_1 a^3 + 3A_2 a^2 + 2A_3 a + A_4 = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$12A_1 a^2 + 6A_2 a + 2A_3 = 0 \quad (12)$$

Similarly, at $x = 0, y = b, \sigma = \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial^2 \sigma}{\partial y^2} = 0$ yields the following:

$$B_1 a^4 + B_2 a^3 + B_3 a^2 + B_4 a + B_5 = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$4B_1 a^3 + 3B_2 a^2 + 2B_3 a + B_4 = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$12B_1 a^2 + 6B_2 a + 2B_3 = 0 \quad (15)$$

Meantime, the joint clamping force F_c and resulting pressure $\sigma(x, y, z)$ satisfy the static equilibrium as follows:

$$F_c = \iint_{\Omega} \sigma dS = \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \int_{d/2}^{\frac{ab}{\sqrt{(a \sin \theta)^2 + (b \cos \theta)^2}}} \sigma(x, y, z) r dr \quad (16)$$

There are 10 unknown constants with only 9 equations. Therefore, an additional condition has to be introduced, which should satisfy the in-plane ellipse distribution, as given in Eq. (17).

$$\sigma(ar \cos \theta, z) = \sigma(br \sin \theta, z) \quad (17)$$

Substituting the Eq. (4) into Eq. (17) and assuming equal coefficients for the highest order polynomial items, the additional condition can be obtained as follows:

$$A_1 = \frac{b^4}{a^4} B_1 \quad (18)$$

Then the parameters A_k and B_k ($k=1\sim 5$) can be obtained by solving Eqs. (8) ~ (18). Therefore, the pressure distribution $\sigma(x, y, z)$ at arbitrary z location under clamping force F_c can be obtained by substituting the A_k and B_k ($k=1\sim 5$) into Eq. (7).

2.4 Joint stiffness for UDL

As shown in Fig. 4, the average deflection of a disk layer of the elliptical cone with thickness dz due to the compressive force is given by:

$$d\bar{\delta} = \frac{1}{A} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \int_{d/2}^{\frac{ab}{\sqrt{(a\sin\theta)^2 + (b\cos\theta)^2}}} \frac{\sigma(x, y, z)}{E_3} r dr \quad (19)$$

where A is the area of the disk layer, which can be expressed as Eq. (20).

$$A = \pi \left[ab - \left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^2 \right] \quad (20)$$

Figure 4 Half model of bolted joint in fully developed envelope.

Substituting Eq. (20) into Eq. (19) and integrating the result gives the overall deflection as:

$$\delta = \frac{2F_c}{\pi E_3 \Delta} \ln \left[\frac{(mL + n - \Delta)(n + \Delta)}{(mL + n + \Delta)(n - \Delta)} \right] \quad (21)$$

where coefficients m , n , t and Δ are given as Eq. (22).

$$\begin{aligned}
m &= (\tan \alpha)(\tan \beta) \\
n &= \frac{\gamma d}{2} (\tan \alpha + \tan \beta) \\
t &= \frac{(\gamma^2 - 1)d^2}{4} \\
\Delta &= \sqrt{n^2 - 4mt}
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Thus, the joint stiffness K_c can be represented by Eq. (23).

$$K_c = \frac{\pi E_3 \Delta}{2 \ln \left[\frac{(mL + n - \Delta)(n + \Delta)}{(mL + n + \Delta)(n - \Delta)} \right]} \tag{23}$$

3 MODEL VALIDATION

FEM was used to validate the AM. The specimen consists of one laminate, one bolt, one nut and two washers. The laminate was made by 10 layers' unidirectional lamina (nominal single layer thickness is 0.188 mm) with geometry of 36x36x1.88 mm and a hole of 6.0 mm, whose mechanical properties were given in Table 1. The M6 bolt and nut were all made by steel with elastic modulus of 200 MPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.3. Mesh and boundary conditions of the specimen were illustrated in Fig. 5. The mesh dependency was conducted from element size of 0.1 mm to 1.0 mm. Finally, in-plane element size in the clamp region within radius of 10 mm was 0.2 mm and that outside the region was 1.0 mm; and through-thickness element size was selected as two elements a layer. The preload of bolt was represented by pressure on surfaces of the bolt and nut. The laminate was fixed at four sides with all freedom degree limited.

Figure 5 Mesh and boundary conditions of the finite element model.

E_1 [GPa]	E_2 [GPa]	ν_{12}	G_{12} [GPa]
165	8.17	0.33	4.27

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the lamina.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To validate the AM model, in-plane pressure envelope and through-thickness pressure distribution were investigated in this study.

First of all, the in-plane pressure envelopes of the FEM result and AM result are compared, as shown in Fig. 6. The middle plane of the laminates was selected as an example. For clear illustration, the pressure envelope boundary was selected as the one-tenth of the maximum pressure value, which was 1.0 MPa. Fig. 6(a) shows the in-plane pressure envelope in the 5-th plane of the laminate from the FEM result, which is absolutely an ellipse. Fig. 6(b) shows the corresponding pressure boundary from AM result and FEM result at the local coordinate ox_5y_5 . It can be seen that the boundary of AM and

FEM are almost same within accept range, especially for the points of the semi-major axis and semi-minor axis. The situations of the other layers are similar as that of the 5-th layer. It can be concluded that the in-plane pressure distribution meets the ellipse envelope for unidirectional laminated bolted joint.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6 In-plane pressure envelopes of the 5-th layer from: (a) FEM result; (b) AM result.

Next study is about the through-thickness pressure distribution, which is illustrated in Fig. 7.

Through-thickness pressure of four typical sampling directions, which are 0° , 45° , 60° and 90° , from the AM result are chosen and compared with that from the FEM result. All four sampling direction situations from the AM results show good agreement with that from the FEM results, which means the fourth order polynomial assumption for through-thickness pressure distribution in the analytical model is reasonable.

Figure 7 Through-thickness pressure distribution for different sampling directions: (a) $\phi = 0^\circ$; (b) $\phi = 45^\circ$; (c) $\phi = 60^\circ$; (d) $\phi = 90^\circ$.

5 CONCLUSIONS

An analytical model based on the assumption that unidirectional laminate has different contact radii at the longitudinal direction and transverse direction was proposed to predict the stiffness of composite bolted joints. An ellipse in-plane pressure distribution and a fourth order polynomial through-thickness pressure distribution was proposed, which have been validated by the finite element method. The results from the analytical method are in accordance with that from the finite element method. The present analytical method can be used to understand the effect of the preload on stiffness of the joints and investigate the stress under the preload.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 51375068, Grant No. 51475073, and Grant No. 51605076), the National Key Basic Research Program of China (Grant No. 2014CB046504), and the Liaoning Province Natural Science Foundation (Grant No. 201602171).

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